

The Study of the Quark-Gluon Plasma with the ALICE-LHC Experiment

Thematic area(s)

Strong Interactions
Instrumentation and Computing

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Abstract

The Quark-Gluon Plasma is a state of matter where quarks and gluons are deconfined from hadrons expected when nuclear matter is taken to high density or temperature. The study of this state is extremely important for the complete understanding of the equation of state of the Quantum Chromodynamics (QCD) and its properties. It can be achieved in laboratory through heavy ion collisions like the ones generated by the LHC (Large Hadron Collider) at CERN and studied through the ALICE experiment. The goal of this project is to significantly contribute to the study of the Quark-Gluon Plasma through a relevant participation in the ALICE experiment, exploring several aspects as data analysis, instrumentation and training of future generations.

Scientific Context

The theory within the Standard Model of Particle Physics that describes the strong interaction is the Quantum Chromodynamics (QCD). It contains the basic ingredients for the description of hadrons in terms of their fundamental constituents, quarks and gluons. The interaction between quarks occurs through gluons, which also interact with each other. QCD has been very successful in describing a large variety of physical phenomena, from the most basic properties of nuclei found in nature to extreme conditions, such as the dynamics inside neutron stars or collisions between elementary particles, either in the atmosphere (cosmic rays) or in large particle accelerators.

Two important features of QCD are asymptotic freedom and confinement. The first-principles understanding of confinement is still an outstanding open question. An important way to study confinement is to create a deconfined medium in high energy heavy ion collisions. In extreme situations of temperature and/or baryon density, confinement in hadrons is no longer a necessary feature of the medium. In this sense, a phase transition to more complex states of matter occurs. The study of these states is

extremely important for the complete understanding of the equation of state of QCD and its properties.

In particular, when the baryonic density is low and the temperature is high, a phase transition is expected to form a deconfined state of quarks and gluons called Quark-Gluon Plasma (QGP). The observation and characterization of this state have important consequences for the detailed understanding of the strong interactions and it is also crucial for a better comprehension of the evolution of our Universe since it is expected that it was in a similar state after few moments from the Big Bang. The observation and investigation of this state of matter allows us to understand in more detail the evolution of the primordial Universe, its expansion and hadronization. The experimental investigation of the existence and characterization of this state of matter is the focus of large accelerators of heavy ions in relativistic energies, such as RHIC (Relativistic Heavy Ion Collider) in the USA and LHC (Large Hadron Collider) in Europe.

The last twenty years of RHIC and LHC data collection have generated a rich knowledge about nuclear matter under extreme temperature conditions. Statistical models that describe the dynamics of heavy ion collisions through a hydrodynamic approach, in apparent thermal and chemical equilibrium, seem to reproduce the relative abundances of the particles formed during the collisions at an equilibrium temperature around 160 MeV and a low chemical potential. The medium created in heavy ion collisions in these accelerators has a high degree of collectivity, very well established in the measurement of the elliptical flow of various particles. The data obtained for the elliptic flow is well explained by hydrodynamic calculations considering a fluid with low viscosity, close to an ideal quantum fluid and considering an equation of state with a partonic phase. Besides, the system formed is highly dissipative, clearly observed in the suppression of high transverse momentum particles coming from the fragmentation of partons in jets.

After the very strong evidence for the Quark-Gluon Plasma formation in relativistic heavy ion collisions, fundamental questions about its properties must be investigated, motivating a whole research program in the LHC, especially within the ALICE experiment, design specifically for such intent.

Objectives

The goal of this project is to significantly contribute to the study of the Quark-Gluon Plasma through a relevant participation in the ALICE experiment of the Large Hadron Collider (LHC). The objectives include not only the development of physics analysis, but also, the development of state-of-the-art instrumentation devices to further enhance the capabilities of the ALICE detector, such as particle detectors, electronics and software support infra-structure. Another major goal of the project is the training of future generation of scientists, through the development of graduate level scientific projects within the ALICE experiment.

Methodology

Strangeness Production in Relativistic Heavy Ion Collisions

Measurement of hadrons with strange quark content is of special interest in heavy ion collisions. The strange quark mass is around the phase transition threshold value making

the production of strange particles an interesting probe for equilibration. Also, strange particle production could be sensitive to different aspects of heavy ion collision dynamics. For instance, in the deconfined Quark Gluon Plasma (QGP) scenario, the gluon-gluon fusion process should enhance the production rate of strange quark-antiquark pairs, hence, increasing the production of strange hadrons. It was indeed one of the originally proposed signatures of the QGP. Compared to a purely hadronic gas scenario, where hadronic reaction rates are too small to allow for equilibration of strange particle densities, the QGP formation would lead to an enhancement of strange hadrons and in particular of multi-strange anti-hyperons. But, also, since the strange quark mass is higher than that of light quarks, strangeness enhancement would depend strongly on the thermodynamic circumstances, and in particular, would decrease the enhancement in the final observed hadrons. A comparison of a plasma system with a hadronic system in equilibrium with the same amount of entropy and baryon number showed that strangeness could be equally abundant in both cases. To disentangle the different scenarios and help in the characterization of the strongly interacting matter created in heavy-ion collisions, it is clear that a systematic measurement of the different strange hadrons is necessary, considering different collision energies and system sizes.

The ALICE experiment has accumulated a large amount of data from LHC Run-2, including pp, p-Pb and Pb-Pb collisions at 5.02 TeV, pp at 13 TeV p-Pb at 8.16 TeV and Xe-Xe at 5.44. In particular, from the heavy-ion run performed in 2018, it was accumulated approximately 400 million Pb-Pb events that have not yet been analyzed for strange baryon production. Also, due to the higher luminosity and higher collision rate, the new data set is such that many of the events have multiple collision pile-up in a single event. It imposes a new challenge to data analysis, because the track multiplicity of the recorded events will be higher, and it will be necessary to separate tracks from different collisions. Therefore, given a large amount of data and the difficulty in having pile-up collisions in single recorded events, new analysis techniques will be required to make the best use of the accumulated data. **In this context, the proposal is to study the application of machine learning techniques and other multivariate analysis tools to process the data set from Run-2.** In particular, the multi-strange baryon measurement that makes use of decay topology reconstruction will be greatly affected by the piling-up of collisions and will require some work to get good efficiency. At the same time, the large amount of data will be important to improve the current measurements, in both low transverse momentum and high transverse momentum p_T region, that have poor statistical significance yet very high physical importance. To improve the measurement efficiency in the low p_T region of multi-strange baryons spectra it is important to reduce the statistical and systematic uncertainty of the integrated yield. The high p_T region is important for fragmentation physics. In particular, particle fragmentation in the strangeness sector is still not well understood, and most models are phenomenological and rely on experimental data to constrain their parameters. Hence, more detailed data in this region is needed, especially in the strangeness sector.

For the next 5 years, within the strangeness analysis in ALICE, it is proposed within this project to analyze the production of strange hadrons, K^0_s , Λ , Ξ and Ω , in the large data sets available for collisions of Pb-Pb, p-Pb and pp at energies of 5.02 TeV and above. To improve reconstruction efficiency, it is proposed to study and apply different

multivariate analysis techniques, including tools based on Machine Learning. Physics wise, the measured particles will be used to study baryon production in heavy ion collisions (baryon anomaly effect and effect of strangeness in statistical thermal models), fragmentation in the strangeness sector (including two-particle correlation and Jet reconstruction using strange particles) and strangeness enhancement. In addition to the analysis of strange baryons mentioned above, it is planned to test the feasibility of applying Machine Learning techniques to other problems such as hypertriton measurements as well as some specific resonance studies. As an example, there is the $K^*(892)^0 \rightarrow K^0 + \gamma$, which is of interest because the photon will not interact with the medium, contrary to the more common charged $K-\pi$ pair typically used for $K^*(892)^0$ reconstruction. Such exploratory studies would involve the same detection techniques as in the standard strange baryon analyses.

QGP Tomography with Hard Probes

The medium created in relativistic heavy ion collisions has a very short average lifetime, with times characteristic of the order of fm/c. In these conditions, it is impossible to use a well-known external probe to test the properties of this medium, as done, for example, in medical computed tomography, in which a well-known and calibrated penetrating probe interacts with the medium. Modification of this probe by the medium can reveal information about the characteristics of this medium. In this case, it is necessary to look for probes that are already available in the initial moments of the collision and are well understood if there is no interaction with the medium.

From this point of view, two probes are particularly interesting: heavy quarks (charm and bottom) and jets. The systematic studies of the production of heavy quarks and jets, in particular jets originating from heavy quarks fragmentation, is an important tool to characterize the properties of the QGP. There are several procedures in order to perform such studies. The direct reconstruction of mesons containing heavy quarks (D for charm and B for bottom) from their hadronic channels of decay is feasible, but it is very difficult in high multiplicity environments, mainly for B mesons. However, a non-negligible fraction (of the order of 10-15%) of these hadron decays through semi-leptonic channels. Thus, the measurement of electrons and di-electrons (electron pairs) provide an alternative tool in the study of the production of heavy quarks.

The study of the production of heavy quarks is also interesting when resonant states (also called quarkonia) are observed, such as J/ψ , ψ' , etc. (charmonium) for c-cbar and Upsilon states (1S, 2S and 3S), for b-bbar (botomonium) states. For a long time, the suppression of J/ψ in nucleus-nucleus collisions due to the Debye Screening was accepted as an unequivocal signature of the phase transition to a quark and gluon plasma. A medium created above the critical temperature (T_c) for the phase transition would make the charmonium states no longer connected. However, recent lattice QCD calculations indicate that some states can survive to very high temperatures compared to the critical temperature. In fact, these calculations foresee a successive dissociation of the various resonant states, according to the binding energy. Added to the melting of these states, other processes, such as absorption in cold matter and recombination can cause an extra suppression or even increase in the production of charmonium. On the other hand, measures of botomonium, due to its smaller radius, compared to

charmonium, are more strongly connected and, because of this, would survive even in very high temperatures.

Therefore, **it is proposed in this project to study within the ALICE experiment, jets originated from heavy quarks, through open and quarkonia states, using mainly electrons as the measuring probe.** Machine learning techniques can also be applied in these studies, broadening the scope of the results obtained so far. As mentioned in the previous section, the ALICE experiment has accumulated a rich amount of data for different energies and colliding systems during Run-2 that can be analyzed with this purpose. The LHC Run-3 will be particularly important for ALICE, since most of the experiment upgrades will be in place for this data taken period and a large sample of data is expected.

The study of the interaction of jets with the medium formed during heavy ion collisions at the high rapidity region is also of great interest since the conditions of the hot and dense matter should change with this quantity, although it is not expected to be a strong dependence. Besides possible changes in the medium properties, other rapidity dependent effects might be important for parton energy loss measurements, as different contributions from quark and gluon fragmentation and the distribution of the initial parton transverse momentum spectrum. The shape of the initial p_T spectrum is very important for the measurement of the single hadron nuclear modification factor at this rapidity region, because high- p_T hadrons at midrapidity come from a wide distribution of parton p_T , while at high rapidity, the kinematic range of parton transverse momentum is limited. Therefore, a stronger suppression is expected at large rapidity compared to midrapidity. **This study can be performed through the measurement of the nuclear modification factor of neutral pions with the ALICE Forward Calorimeter (FoCal), a new detector proposed for the LHC Run-4,** as discussed below in this text.

List of the interested scientists in the community

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Current status and expected challenges

The ALICE experiment upgrade program is concentrated in the LHC Run-3, from 2021 to 2024. The major goal of the experiment is to precisely characterize the QGP, increasing the accumulated data sample significantly through a high rate capability (50 kHz for Pb–Pb collisions) in a near minimum bias mode. This task will be accomplished by building a new Inner Tracking System and by modifying all major ALICE detectors to provide a fully pipelined read-out, with a major upgrade of the data acquisition and high-level trigger systems.

For the Run-3 upgrade, the Brazilian groups have provided major contribution through the full development of a new front-end readout chip for two ALICE detectors, the Time

Projection Chamber (TPC) and the Muon Chamber (MCH), and the construction of the mechanical support of the new Muon Forward Tracker (MFT). The groups intend to continue contributing to these systems along the Run-3, as described below.

Recently, the ALICE collaboration has proposed two upgrades for the LHC Run-4 as well: a new inner layer of the Silicon Inner Tracker System (ITS), called ITS3, and a Forward Calorimeter (FoCal). The Brazilian groups intend to contribute to the later, as described below as well.

ALICE Upgrade for LHC Run-3

The ALICE Upgrade program includes the replacement of the TPC readout planes, previously composed of Multi-Wire Proportional Chambers (MWPC), with the newer technology of Micro-Patterned Gaseous Detectors (MPGDs). The choice was to adopt a four-stage amplification of Gas Electron Multipliers (GEM), motivated by its better performance (mainly Ion Back Flow taming) and suitability to fit in the TPC layout. This choice aims the enhancement of the TPC efficiency, since it allows the continuous measurement instead of the gated mode needed by the MWPC in use until recently.

The new technology offers better resistance against aging – i.e., loss of performance due to the radiation-induced deterioration of its constituents – leading to an expected extended live-time and better long-time stability. However, there is still some unclarity regarding the effects and consequences of long-term aging, and more importantly, there is a lack of diagnostic tools and strategies to mitigate its effects.

In this context, the Brazilian participation includes the study of aging and the search for strategies to mitigate its effects. For that, a collaboration program was established with the University of Nottingham to better understand the surface chemical reaction that occurs at the electrodes inside the Gas Electron Multiplier (GEM), which is the major effect that is responsible for the aging. Besides, developing methods for diagnostics of the GEM at the TPC with the minor intervention is of high interest. For that, in this project is proposed to use Dielectric Relaxation Spectroscopy (DRS) as a non-invasive method to assess the deterioration of the GEM constituents. The target is to develop a protocol of analysis, establishing a relation between aging effects and measured signal by DRS.

ALICE Upgrade for LHC Run-4

The FoCal is a high-granularity calorimeter localized in the very high rapidity region (forward) of the experiment adding new capabilities to ALICE experiment. The strategy adopted by the FoCal proposal is to measure π^0 decays at forward rapidity up to large transverse momenta ($p_T \sim 20$ GeV/c). Due to the longitudinal momentum boost of a forward rapidity measurement, the detector must allow the identification of the decay photons with great precision, reconstructing photon pairs with spatial separation of a few mm at the surface of the detector. Such measurement results in precise discrimination between direct photons and decay photons, making it possible to measure direct photons and π^0 decays in a broad p_T range from low to large values of rapidity.

The layout of the proposed detector is composed of a high-granularity electromagnetic calorimeter in front of a hadronic calorimeter outside the ALICE solenoid magnet at a distance of 7 m from the colliding beam point. The electromagnetic calorimeter follows a compact silicon-tungsten (Si+W) sampling with a longitudinal segmentation design. The current proposal consists of 18 layers of tungsten and silicon pads with low granularity ($\sim 1 \text{ cm}^2$) and two (or three) layers of tungsten and silicon pixels with high granularity ($\sim 30 \times 30 \mu\text{m}^2$). The pad layers will allow the measurement of the shower energy and profile, and the pixel layers will provide two-photon separation with high spatial precision in order to discriminate between isolated photons and merged showers of decay photon pairs from neutral pions. The proposal for the hadronic calorimeter is to have a steel or Pb/scintillating fiber spaghetti calorimeter with a high granularity of up to $2.5 \times 2.5 \text{ cm}^2$, providing good hadronic resolution and compensation.

The aimed contribution in this project is the R&D and construction of the FoCal Silicon Pad layers readout system. Given the large experience of the group with the development of the SAMPA chip, which will instrument the ALICE TPC and MCH detectors beyond Run-3, it is natural to expect that a significant contribution to this part of the project can be achieved.

Timeline

The goals discussed in this white paper concerns the Brazilian participation in the ALICE experiment during the next 6 or 7 years, including the LHC Run 3, from May 2021 to the end of 2024, and the preparation for the LHC Run 4, during the Long Shutdown 3, from 2025 to mid-2027. The data to be analyzed comes from the LHC Run 2 and Run 3. The studies regarding the upgrades for Run 3 will be carried on until the end of 2024 and the preparation for the upgrades of Run 4 starts now and should extend until the end of 2026.

Construction and operational costs

Maintenance and Operation

The participation in any large international collaboration foresees a shared contribution from all groups and institutions involved for the maintenance and operation of the experiment. In the case of the ALICE experiment, there are two kinds of Maintenance and Operation (M&O) contributions. The so-called M&O-A that corresponds to the basic and general costs of the experiment. This contribution is due to the experiment yearly and the total amount of required funds is divided among all PhD authors in the collaboration. For instance, the expected contribution from the Brazilian groups in ALICE in 2020 is 78,059 CHF for 10 Scientists.

Another kind of Maintenance and Operation (M&O) contribution in ALICE is the so-called M&O-B, that corresponds to the expenses regarding specific detectors. These costs are shared among the groups that have contributed significantly with the construction of a given detector. The Brazilian groups in ALICE have participated in the construction and upgrade of two ALICE detectors, the Time Projection Chamber (TPC) and the Muon Forward Tracker (MFT). Therefore, it is expected a contribution in terms of M&O-B for these two systems of the ALICE experiment around 20,000 CHF per year.

Contribution for the ALICE TPC Aging Studies

Regarding the studies on aging of the GEMs for the ALICE TPC, the estimated costs include the construction of a degradation chamber that shall be used for submitting GEM prototypes similar to those installed in the TPC under extreme simulated conditions of use. By extreme conditions of use is understood as a high-count rate condition for long periods. During the degradation, the characterization of the gas that circulates inside the detector can provide information on the gaseous chemical products consequence of the avalanche of ionization and outgas of internal parts triggered by radiation. Besides, the major reason for GEM irreversible damaging is the loss of electrical insulation of the dielectric part of the amplification foil. The adoption of DRS can provide quantitative information on the insulating conditions of the dielectric and, with systematical studies, can become a useful and non-invasive tool for diagnosing the TPC.

In this sense, one equipment for gas composition characterization with low detection limits for hydrogen and hydrocarbons, together with other equipment for DRS measurements constitute the major investments. The surface characterization will be executed by our collaborators at the University of Nottingham. The estimated budget for this part is of approximately 180,000 CHF, not including costs with human resources.

Contribution for FoCal Pad Detectors Readout System

The FoCal pad layers will be composed of silicon pad sensors with a granularity of 1×1 cm produced in 6-inch wafers. The analog signals from the pad sensors must go through a charge sensitive amplifier-shaper and digitized to ship the data on a standard digital connection (GBTX), as performed by the SAMPA chip. However, an important design consideration for the FoCal pad layers is the dynamic range. For measurements in the forward direction, it is necessary to measure showers with energies of up to 2 TeV ($p_T = 16$ GeV/c at $\eta = 5.5$), but also detect Minimum Ionizing Particle (MIP) signals in order to calibrate the sensors. These two extremes generate charge signals from a few fC to several pC. The energy resolution expected to achieve at the high p_T region is around a percent for showers (a few percent per pad), resulting in a total dynamic range of about 10^5 . Such a large dynamic range and high precision can only be reached with a dual-range readout. A very good candidate for a readout chip is the HGCROC chip being developed by the CMS collaboration. This chip has a dual-range readout where an ADC can provide the measurement for signals up to 100 MIP and a time-over-threshold mechanism to measure large signals. HGCROC samples the signals at the LHC frequency of 40 MHz and sends out signals above a threshold.

The complete readout system for the FoCal pad layers is still in the research and development phase, mainly by the ALICE group in the Laboratory of Subatomic Physics & Cosmology (LPSC) in Grenoble. Given the experience of the Brazilian groups with detector readout systems, the aim is to contribute with this effort in the near future significantly. The total cost of the FoCal pad layers readout system is estimated in 500,000 CHF and the current proposal is to share such cost (around 50%) with the LPSC group.

Computing requirements

The experiments of the CERN LHC accelerator generate an unprecedented amount of data that needs to be stored and processed safely and efficiently. This unique condition of the LHC has spurred the creation of a new technology called GRID. The concept behind this new technology is to replace the creation of a single (or a few) data storage and processing center, which construction and maintenance would be beyond the capabilities of any organization on the globe, with the use of numerous smaller data processing centers scattered around the planet. This technology allowed all LHC collaborations to establish the so-called **fair share** approach for the storage and processing of data generated in the accelerator, where this huge task is fairly and equally divided among all members of the collaborations, with each group or institution taking over the commitment to provide data storage and processing capacity commensurate with their numerical participation in the collaboration. Therefore, in the specific case of the Brazilian groups that are part of the ALICE collaboration, this fraction for 2020 is 2%, with possible year-by-year fluctuations, due to the flow of researchers in these groups. Given the above, one can obtain the expected contribution of the groups from Brazil participating in the ALICE experiment by calculating this fraction (2%) of the total resources needed for the experiment, both in terms of processing (given in kHESPEC06 units) and storage (in PB).

The ALICE groups in Brazil have been providing its fair share contribution to the experiment since 2007 through the SAMPA cluster (acronym from the Portuguese, *Sistema de Análise e Multi-Processamento Avançado*), hosted in the Physics Institute of Universidade de São Paulo. Currently, the cluster has 2408 CPU cores, totalizing 18.7 kHS06 of processing power and 0.85 PB of storage. However, it is important to highlight that part of this processing capability, around 6 kHS06, is used by local users, outside the GRID.

The total amount of resources needed is set by each experiment and carefully reviewed by CERN's Computer Resources Scrutiny Group (CRSG). In October 2019, the CRSG published its latest report on the resources claimed by the collaborations and evaluated by this group¹. **Table 1** shows the request from the ALICE collaboration for 2020 and 2021 as mentioned in this document and the share of the ALICE groups in Brazil. The fair share is the fraction of the total requested for Tier 1 and Tier 2 sites.

ALICE	2020			2021		
	T1	T2	Fair Share SP (2% of T1+T2)	T1	T2	Fair Share SP (2% of T1+T2)
CPU (kHS06)	365	376	14.82	365	376	14.82
Disk (PB)	44.0	39.0	1.66	53.3	44.8	1.962

Table 1: ALICE Experiment request for data processing and storage¹ for 2020 and 2021

For the following years (from 2022 to 2025, up to the end of LHC Run 3), the expectation is an increase in the demand for data processing and storage of 20% per year. This increasing demand is consequence of the higher luminosity of the LHC for Run3 (from

¹ Fall 2019 Report of the Computing Resources Scrutiny Group, CERN-RRB-2019-079, 14 October 2019

2021 to 2025), when the rate of data production will be considerably increased. **Table 2** shows an estimation of the requested processing power given the values in **Table 1** and the expected 20% growth for the following years (second column). The third column shows the computing power aimed for each year, while the fourth column shows the number of extra Compute Modules necessary in order to achieve such proposal given the computing model adopted and the considered processing power of the individual Compute Modules. In this table, it is considered an evolution of 20% in the processing power of the Compute Modules every 2 years.

	Requested Processing Power (kHS06)	Proposed Processing Power (kHS06)	Extra Compute Modules for the SAMPA cluster	Processing Power per Compute Module (kHS06)
2019	14,8	18,7		
2020	14,8	18,7		
2021	20,3	20,6	3	0,62
2022	24,3	24,3	6	0,62
2023	29,2	29,6	7	0,75
2024	35,0	35,5	8	0,75
2025	42,0	42,7	8	0,90
TOTAL			32	

Table 2: Expect growth of the processing power of the computer cluster assuming 20% per year increase in the demand and 20% evolution every 2 years of the processing power of the compute modules

In terms of storage, the same approach is used as shown in **Table 3**. In this case, it is considered a growth of single disk capacity of 2 TB every 2 years, as it has been the pattern in the last years.

	Requested Disk Storage (PB)	Proposal Disk Storage (PB)	Number of Extra Disks for the SAMPA Cluster	Single Disk Capacity (TB)
2019	0,85			
2020	1,66	1,67	68	12
2021	1,96	1,97	26	12
2022	2,35	2,37	29	14
2023	2,83	2,83	34	14
2024	3,39	3,40	36	16
2025	4,07	4,08	43	16
TOTAL			236	

Table 3: Expect growth of the storage power of the computer cluster assuming 20% per year increase in the demand and 20% evolution every 2 years of single disk capacity

It is crucial to emphasize that the fair share contribution to the experiment data processing and storage is a crucial pillar for the big LHC experiments to function

properly. Therefore, this contribution is a very basic requirement for a relevant participation in these collaborations.